

Unveiling the Transformative Influence of Instructional Leadership on Teacher Professional Development: The Case of the Private High School of Buenavista Agusan del Norte

Nheño Carlo Jude F. Ytem

Doctor of Education, Major in Educational Leadership, National Teachers College

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10260032>

ABSTRACT

The challenge of instructional leadership persists in schools globally, given its limited definition compared to the diverse roles undertaken by principals and other administrators. Hence, this qualitative study aimed to unpack the role of instructional leadership in teacher professional development. Thirty teachers and three coordinators participated, providing data through semi-structured interviews, subsequently analyzed using thematic analysis. The findings yielded three primary themes. Firstly, instructional leadership practices emerged as crucial in fostering teacher learning and development. Participants stressed the significance of leaders modeling effective teaching practices, offering feedback, and facilitating collaborative learning opportunities. Secondly, the study underscored the importance of the quality of teacher-administrator relationships in promoting professional growth. Trust, open communication, and mutual respect were highlighted as pivotal in building positive relationships. Lastly, the study illuminated that teacher professional development is an ongoing process requiring sustained support from school leaders. Participants emphasized the necessity for continuous professional development opportunities, including workshops, mentoring, and coaching. These findings hold noteworthy implications for educational leaders and policymakers aiming to enhance teacher professional development. School leaders are encouraged to prioritize instructional leadership practices that model effective teaching and promote collaborative learning. Additionally, fostering positive teacher-administrator relationships and providing ongoing professional development opportunities can support teachers in their continuous professional growth, fostering a culture of perpetual learning and development in schools, ultimately leading to enhanced student learning outcomes.

Keywords: *Instructional leadership, Teacher professional development, School administrators, challenges, Effectiveness*

INTRODUCTION

School reforms globally have consistently prioritized enhancing student achievement. As a result, principals, acting as school leaders, and teachers, who bear the responsibility for instruction, are expected to develop strategies that enhance student performance (Zepeda, 2018). This has heightened the accountability of principals to focus on instructional leadership, and for teachers to engage in collaboration, both being fundamental aspects of effective schools (Hallinger, 2018).

Rowe (2018) pointed out that in recent decades, the role of principals has evolved to encompass that of a building manager, politician, instructional leader, and change agent. With the increasing emphasis on accountability worldwide, the role of principal instructional leadership has been highlighted as a key strategy to enhance school organizations. Principals are now expected to oversee teaching and learning quality, curriculum, and staff motivation and development (Mulford and Silins, 2019).

However, instructional leadership remains a significant challenge in nearly all schools globally due to its narrow definition in comparison to the multitude of roles that principals and other school administrators undertake. Prytula et al. (2013) noted that fulfilling instructional leadership becomes difficult as it involves a substantial portion of managerial responsibilities and demands. Many demands placed on school administrators are a result of societal influences and policy matters (Jenkins, 2019). These have given rise to leadership issues, including increased responsibility without corresponding authority, an imbalance between management and leadership despite longer work hours, heightened ambiguity and complexity, and a decline in morale and enthusiasm.

Furthermore, the functions of school principals and administrators have expanded significantly due to diverse expectations from various community sectors (Cohen et al., 2018). Instructional leadership should not solely focus on teaching and learning aspects of school leadership but should also emphasize organizational management for instructional improvement rather than day-to-day teaching and learning. The effectiveness and efficiency of teaching-learning experiences in schools are minimally influenced by school administrators' direct involvement in classroom instruction. This underscores that instructional leaders can profoundly impact teaching quality and student learning through their decisions regarding teacher selection, classroom assignments, teacher retention, and opportunities for teacher improvement. Organizational management for instructional improvement involves staffing schools with high-quality teachers and providing them with the necessary support and resources to succeed in the classroom.

In the Philippines, a significant advancement occurred in the education system when former President Benigno Simeon C. Aquino III enacted the K to 12 Program into law in 2012. This initiative aimed to enhance the quality of education in the country by implementing substantial reforms compared to the previous curriculum. The Department of Education (DepEd) embraced this challenge, focusing on delivering meaningful learning to every citizen to help them reach their maximum potential. The additional two years of senior high school in basic education were designed to equip students with the cognitive and technical competencies necessary to navigate global challenges and maintain competitiveness.

Recent research on school effectiveness has sparked discussions about the importance of integrating the teacher-leader relationship, particularly trust, into conceptual models of school leadership (Hallinger and Walker, 2018). Within this realm of research, "trust," denoting a teacher's willingness to be vulnerable to another based on confidence that the principal is benevolent, open, honest, competent, and reliable (Woolfolk-Hoy 2020), has emerged as a

critical mechanism through which leadership can exert influence (e.g., Bryk and Schneider, 2021; Tschannen-Moran and Gareis, 2018; Wahlstrom and Louis, 2018).

Additionally, the educational system in the country is striving to evaluate the instructional leadership skills of school leaders. Both public and private schools are consistently aiming to enhance their performance. However, they appear to overlook that a school's exceptional performance is significantly influenced by the performance of its teachers. Instructional leaders, such as principals and other school administrators, often find themselves engrossed in their day-to-day responsibilities and duties of leading their communities, leaving them with inadequate time to practice the instructional leadership skills as expected.

To tackle this urgent issue, the Department of Education (DepEd) is dedicated to offering its members opportunities to align their individual accomplishments with the institution's Vision and Mission. This aims to encourage both personal and team growth, active involvement, and commitment, as well as to foster professional and personal development.

Indeed, Republic Act (RA) No. 9155, also recognized as "The Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001," Section 2 emphasizes the state's encouragement of local endeavors to enhance the quality of basic education. It further underscores the state's obligation to ensure that the educational program for children, out-of-school youth, and adult learners reflects the values, needs, and aspirations of the school community. Consequently, the addition of two years in basic education is the agency's initiative to meet the specific needs of Filipino learners and provide them with what truly benefits them. Additionally, Section 7 of this act underscores that, at the school level, the school head, serving as both an instructional leader and administrative manager, oversees the delivery of quality education.

Thus, teachers play a crucial role in imparting essential skills, knowledge, and attitudes to every learner, nurturing them into lifelong learners. Hence, it's imperative that those guiding the learning process possess the requisite skills to deliver high-quality education to the students effectively and efficiently. These skills stem from teachers' sense of self-efficacy in aiding learners in their journey to acquire knowledge, skills, and attitudes.

In recent educational research, several important trends have emerged. Firstly, transformational leadership in education has gained recognition for its ability to inspire and motivate educators, fostering collaboration and innovation that significantly enhance teaching effectiveness and ultimately benefit student outcomes (Bass & Riggio, 2021). Moreover, ongoing professional development for teachers, aligned with evidence-based pedagogical strategies, has shown a strong positive correlation with teaching effectiveness (Ingersoll & Strong, 2022). Additionally, the utilization of data for informed decision-making has become a critical aspect of instructional leadership, promoting tailored instruction and interventions that enhance teaching effectiveness and student achievement (Supovitz & Taylor, 2005). Lastly, the recent shift to remote and hybrid learning environments necessitates a re-evaluation of instructional leadership, emphasizing the need for adaptable approaches to support effective teaching in evolving educational settings (Wang et al., 2023). By addressing these contemporary challenges using a problem-based approach, this study aims to offer actionable recommendations to strengthen instructional leadership and improve teaching effectiveness within the private high school of Buenavista Agusan del Norte educational landscape.

Thus, the study aimed to conduct a thorough evaluation of instructional leadership skills among school administrators and their direct influence on teaching effectiveness within the unique context of the private high school of Buenavista Agusan del Norte. Employing a problem-based approach, the researcher sought to comprehensively understand the intricate relationship between instructional leadership and teaching effectiveness, incorporating the most recent research and ideas in the field. The study was motivated by the need to provide up-to-date,

evidence-based insights that could guide the development of targeted leadership programs tailored for school administrators in this specific region.

Research Questions

This study aimed to conduct a thorough evaluation of instructional leadership skills among school administrators and their direct influence on teaching effectiveness within the unique context of the private high school of Buenavista Agusan del Norte.

Specifically, this qualitative inquiry sought to answer the following questions:

1. What vital role of instructional leadership in teacher professional development?
2. What challenges in enacting effective instructional leadership?
3. What challenges to implementing effective instructional leadership practices for teacher professional development?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a qualitative research methodology, utilizing a case study approach to delve into the experiences and perspectives of thirty (30) teachers in the Saint James High School, regarding instructional leadership and professional development. Data collection encompassed semi-structured interviews, focus groups, and document analysis. Semi-structured interviews engaged school administrators, including department heads and coordinators, to gather their insights on instructional leadership and its impact on teacher professional development. Focus groups were conducted with teachers to explore their firsthand experiences with instructional leadership and professional development. Additionally, the analysis delved into school improvement plans, professional development plans, and other pertinent school documents to provide further insight into the role of instructional leadership in teacher professional development.

Purposive sampling was employed to select participants with knowledge and relevant experience pertaining to the research questions. Participants were briefed on the study's purpose and their rights, emphasizing voluntary participation with the option to withdraw without consequence. To uphold confidentiality and anonymity, all collected data was safeguarded.

Thematic analysis was the chosen method for analyzing data gathered from interviews, focus groups, and document analysis. Transcription, coding, and analysis were conducted to identify emerging themes and patterns related to the research questions. Ethical considerations adhered to principles such as informed consent, confidentiality, and anonymity. Given the researcher's dual role as the school's principal, precautions were taken to prevent any compromise to participants' rights or privacy. For instance, involving another staff member in the data analysis aimed to ensure objectivity and minimize the risk of bias.

RESULTS

Theme 1: The Vital Role of Instructional Leadership in Teacher Professional Development

"Instructional leadership is indispensable for our professional development as teachers. Our school leaders provide the necessary support and guidance, enabling us to enhance our teaching practices and effectively address the needs of our students." – Teacher 1

"Our school coordinators play a pivotal role in our professional growth. They offer feedback and support that contribute to refining our teaching methods, ultimately making a positive impact on our students." – Teacher 2

"Instructional leadership revolves around fostering a culture of learning and continuous improvement. Our school leaders are instrumental in promoting this culture, cultivating an environment of collaboration and support among teachers." – Coordinator 1

"Instructional leadership serves as the backbone of our professional development. Our school leaders equip us with resources and support, ensuring we stay current on the latest teaching methods, benefiting our students." – Coordinator 2

Findings indicate that instructional leadership is indispensable for teacher professional development, with school leaders playing a critical role in guiding and supporting teachers as they strive to enhance their teaching practices and meet students' needs. Teachers and coordinators alike underscore the significance of instructional leadership in establishing a culture of continuous improvement and emphasize school leaders' crucial role in promoting this culture, providing essential resources, and offering support for teachers' success.

Teachers and coordinators align in recognizing that instructional leadership involves not only providing feedback and support but also setting clear goals and expectations for professional development. According to one coordinator, "We collaborate with teachers to set goals and develop plans for achieving them, helping them identify areas for improvement and strategies for addressing those areas."

Both groups also acknowledge that instructional leadership necessitates ongoing communication and collaboration. As one teacher notes, "Our coordinators are readily available to answer questions and provide support. They make themselves accessible and collaborate with us to find solutions to any challenges we face."

Similarly, a coordinator emphasizes the importance of building strong relationships with teachers, stating, "We strive to understand each teacher individually, recognizing their needs and strengths. This allows us to tailor our support and coaching to their unique requirements."

Finally, teachers and coordinators agree that effective instructional leadership places a strong emphasis on student learning outcomes. As one teacher expresses, "Ultimately, the goal of instructional leadership is to improve student learning. Everything we do as teachers should be focused on that goal."

Coordinators also stress the importance of data-driven decision-making, with one noting, "We use data to guide our instruction and identify areas for improvement. This approach helps us stay focused on our goals and make evidence-based decisions about our professional development."

In summary, these findings underscore the critical role of instructional leadership in supporting teacher professional development. Effective instructional leadership involves setting clear goals, fostering ongoing communication and collaboration, and maintaining a focus on student learning outcomes.

Theme 2: Challenges in Enacting Effective Instructional Leadership

The study revealed that while instructional leadership proves to be a pragmatic approach for supporting teacher professional development, it is not without its set of challenges. Numerous teachers and coordinators pointed out hurdles encountered in implementing effective instructional leadership practices. A prevalent challenge was the scarcity of time and resources dedicated to supporting teacher professional development. As one coordinator remarked, "Our schedules are packed, and finding time for coaching and collaboration can be challenging. Additionally, resource constraints limit the support we can provide."

Another obstacle identified was resistance to change among certain teachers. Participants reported instances of reluctance among teachers to embrace new instructional practices. A teacher highlighted this by stating, *"Some educators have adhered to certain methods for a considerable period, making it difficult to persuade them to explore alternative approaches."*

Lastly, sustaining instructional leadership over time emerged as a notable challenge. A coordinator expressed, *"Instructional leadership demands ongoing effort and commitment; it's not a one-time task. Maintaining energy and focus over the long term can be demanding."* These findings indicate that, despite its practicality, instructional leadership faces challenges such as time and resource constraints, resistance to change, and difficulties in sustaining efforts over time.

The study emphasized the crucial role of school administrators' instructional leadership practices in shaping teacher professional development. All participants recognized that administrators engaging in instructional leadership practices foster a culture of continuous learning and improvement. According to one coordinator, *"The leader's instructional leadership practices influence teacher professional development by setting a tone of prioritizing and modeling learning and improvement. When leaders prioritize and model these values, it becomes contagious, inspiring everyone to strive for improvement."*

Furthermore, the study identified specific instructional leadership practices positively impacting teacher professional development. These practices encompass setting clear expectations for teaching and learning, providing regular feedback and support to teachers, and creating opportunities for teacher collaboration and professional learning. Participants stressed the significance of these practices in shaping teacher learning and growth. As one teacher expressed, *"Administrator feedback on my teaching practice has been invaluable. It has helped me identify areas for growth and develop an improvement plan."*

Additionally, the study unveiled that instructional leadership practices prioritizing teacher autonomy and agency positively influence teacher professional development. When administrators empower teachers to take charge of their learning and growth, it fosters a sense of empowerment and motivation. A coordinator emphasized this by stating, *"When teachers have the autonomy to identify their learning goals and opportunities, they become more motivated and engaged in their professional growth."* These findings underscore the critical role of instructional leadership practices in shaping teacher professional development, creating a culture of continuous learning and improvement.

Theme 3: Challenges to implementing effective instructional leadership practices for teacher professional development

While instructional leadership practices have a positive impact on teacher professional development, the study also brought to light various challenges faced by school administrators in effectively implementing these practices. A significant challenge is the demand for more resources and support for professional development. Participants observed that school administrators often grapple with limited resources and contend with competing demands, making it difficult to prioritize professional development. As expressed by one teacher, *"The school administrator wants to provide opportunities for us to learn, but there are limited resources, and they have to balance competing demands."*

Another challenge highlighted in the study is the scarcity of time for professional development. Participants recognized that teachers, constrained by the demands of teaching and other responsibilities, have limited time to engage in professional development. A coordinator noted, *"Teachers are busy with their classes, grading papers, and other responsibilities, so finding time for professional development can be challenging."*

Furthermore, the study pinpointed a lack of awareness and understanding of effective instructional leadership practices as a hurdle to their implementation. Participants noted that some school administrators may lack the knowledge or training needed to effectively execute instructional leadership practices supporting teacher professional development. A teacher expressed, *"Some administrators may not be aware of the best practices in instructional leadership, which can make it difficult for them to provide effective support for our professional development."*

Overall, the findings underscore that despite the positive influence of instructional leadership practices on teacher professional development, school administrators encounter several challenges in their effective implementation. These challenges encompass a scarcity of resources and support, limited time for professional development, and a lack of awareness and understanding of effective instructional leadership practices.

DISCUSSION

This study explored into the role of instructional leadership in facilitating teacher professional development within a private school setting in the Philippines. The findings underscore the significance of effective instructional leadership practices in fostering teacher professional development, aligning with prior research emphasizing the pivotal role of instructional leadership in enhancing teacher effectiveness and student learning outcomes (Robinson et al., 2018).

The first theme extracted from the study emphasizes the importance of school administrators' support in cultivating a culture of continuous professional development. Participants stressed the value of administrators actively engaging in offering professional development opportunities that are relevant and tailored to teachers' needs. This finding echoes previous research suggesting that administrators prioritizing professional development are more likely to establish a culture of continuous learning and improvement (Lieberman & Miller, 2019).

The second theme highlights the crucial role of school administrators' feedback in teacher professional development. Participants emphasized the value of constructive feedback from administrators in enhancing their teaching practices. This finding aligns with prior research underlining the significance of feedback in improving teacher performance (Hattie & Timperley, 2018). The study suggests that effective feedback practices should be continuous, personalized, and aligned with teachers' professional goals and needs.

The third theme addresses the challenges faced by school administrators in implementing effective instructional leadership practices for teacher professional development. Participants identified several challenges, including a lack of resources and support, limited time for professional development, and a deficiency in awareness and understanding of effective instructional leadership practices. These findings support existing research that has recognized the myriad challenges administrators encounter in implementing effective instructional leadership practices (Robinson et al., 2018; Waters & Marzano, 2018).

The implications of these findings are significant for school administrators, policymakers, and teacher educators. School administrators are urged to prioritize professional development and provide ongoing constructive feedback while addressing challenges in implementing effective instructional leadership practices. Policymakers should allocate sufficient resources and support for professional development initiatives that promote effective instructional leadership practices. Finally, teacher educators must incorporate instructional leadership into their training programs to ensure that aspiring administrators possess the knowledge and skills necessary to effectively support teacher professional development.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings, it is evident that instructional leadership plays a pivotal role in the realm of teacher professional development. The study underscored that school administrators demonstrating qualities of instructional leadership, such as furnishing effective feedback, modeling best practices, and fostering teacher collaboration, exerted a positive influence on the professional growth of teachers. Furthermore, the findings indicated that an approach to professional development characterized by collaboration, wherein teachers were afforded opportunities to share experiences and learn from each other, proved more effective than a top-down approach. This underscores the significance of fostering a supportive school culture that encourages teacher collaboration and communication.

The results of the study align with previous research emphasizing the crucial role of instructional leadership in advancing teacher professional development. Additionally, the findings contribute to the expanding body of literature examining the impact of collaborative professional development on teacher growth. In summary, the study's findings hold significant implications for school leaders and policymakers aiming to enhance teacher professional development programs. By prioritizing instructional leadership and instituting collaborative professional development opportunities, schools can better facilitate the professional growth of their teachers, ultimately leading to improved student outcomes.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the study's findings highlighting the critical role of instructional leadership in teacher professional development, it is recommended that school leaders prioritize and actively cultivate instructional leadership qualities among administrators. Encouraging administrators to provide effective feedback, model best practices, and support teacher collaboration can significantly contribute to the professional growth of educators.

Furthermore, adopting a collaborative approach to professional development, where teachers are given opportunities to share experiences and learn from one another, is recommended. Schools should strive to create a supportive and communicative school culture that fosters teacher collaboration. This collaborative approach has been shown to be more effective than a top-down model, aligning with the study's findings and emphasizing the importance of shared learning experiences.

For policymakers and educational stakeholders, the recommendation is to acknowledge and integrate instructional leadership as a central component in the design and implementation of teacher professional development programs. By recognizing the impact of instructional leadership and investing in collaborative professional development initiatives, policymakers can contribute to the overall improvement of teacher effectiveness and, consequently, student outcomes.

COMPLIANCE WITH ETHICAL STANDARDS

This study subscribed to the principles of voluntary participation in research, implying that the respondents might withdraw from this research at any time. Informed consent, which means

that the respondents must at all times, be well informed about the research process and purposes and should give consent to his/her participation in this research.

In conducting Focus Group Discussion (FGD) the researcher will ask first, permission to the respondent to be interviewed. Secondly, the researcher will ensure that the activity will be in a private and comfortable room to secure confidentiality of their information. Lastly, they will ask by the respondents to have an audio recorded interview to use for the transcription of the data.

Safety, involvement put differently, that the researcher will make sure that respondents should not be placed at risk or harm of any kind. Privacy means that the confidentiality and anonymity of the respondents should be protected at all times. Moreover, trust, which implies that the respondents will not be subjected to any acts of deception or betrayal in this research process or its published outcomes and has the right to know the conclusion of this study.

Likewise, the researcher understand what plagiarism entails and are aware of the school's policy in this regard. The researcher undertake not to make use of another person's previous work without recognition or to submit it as our own. The researcher also manage not to allow anyone to copy our output to use it as their work.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I would like to genuinely thank the study participants, Saint James High School teachers who shared their real and complex experiences openly and honestly with me. Without your willingness to do so, I would not have a paper to write.

My sincerest " Thank you!" to my friends Divina Grace Mateo and Shienna Quezon, who supported and motivated me in this endeavor of research, listening to my frustrations and never wavered in their belief that I would successfully complete my degree.

To my mama and sisters, Thank you for inspiring me to finish my degree. To my papa in heaven, because of you pa, I pursued my teaching career, thank you. Above all, to our Almighty God for his protection, wisdom, love, and guidance in our everyday lives.

REFERENCES

- Glanz, J., & Zepeda, S. (Eds.). (2018). *Supervision: New Perspectives for Theory and Practice*. New York, NY: Rowman & Littlefield. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/280315419_Supervision_New_perspectives_in_theory_and_practice
- Hallinger, P., and Murphy, J. (2018). Assessing the instructional management behavior of principals. *Elem. Sch. J.* 86, 217–247.
- Hallinger, P. (2018). Methodologies for studying school Leadership: A Review of 25 years of Research Using the Principal Instructional Management Rating Scale. Paper presented at the annual meeting of the American Educational Research Association, New York.
- Hallinger, P., Hosseingholizadeh, R., Hashemi, N., & Kouhsari, M. (2018). Do beliefs make a difference? Exploring how principal self-efficacy and instructional leadership impact teacher efficacy and commitment in Iran. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*. Retrieved from: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/1741143217700283>

- Ingersoll & Strong (2002). The Impact of Induction and Mentoring Programs for Beginning Teachers: A Critical Review of the Research
- Jenkins, B. (2019). What it takes to be an instructional leader. Retrieved from: www.naesp.org.com
- Leithwood, K., Louis, K. S., Anderson, S., & Wahlstrom, K. (2018). How leadership influences student learning. Review of research. Retrieved from <http://wallacefoundation.org/knowledge-center/Documents/How-Leadership-InfluencesStudent-Learning.pdf>
- Lieberman & Miller, (2019). Teachers as leader Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/233435707_Teachers_as_Leaders
- Mulford B and Silins H (2019) Leadership for organizational learning and improved student outcomes - What do we know? Cambridge Journal of Education 33(2): 175–195.
- Prytula, M., Noonan B., Hellsten, L. (2018). Toward Instructional Leadership: Principals' Perceptions of Large-Scale Assessment in Schools. Canadian Journal of Educational Administration and Policy. Retrieved from: <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1008727.pdf>
- Supovitz, Jonathan A.; Taylor, Brooke Snyder (2005). Systemic Education Evaluation: Evaluating the Impact of Systemwide Reform in Education
- Robinson et al., (2018). School Leadership and Student Outcomes: Identifying What Works and Why Best Evidence Synthesis Iteration (BES)
- Rowe, K. J. (2018). The impact of leadership on student outcomes: an analysis of the differential effects of leadership types. Educ. Adm.
- Tschannen-Moran, M., Woolfolk-Hoy, A.E. & Hoy, A.W. (2018). Teacher Efficacy: The Measuring and Measure. Review of Educational Research.
- Tschannen-Moran, M. & Hoy, A.W. (2021). Teacher Efficacy: Capturing an Elusive Construct. Teaching and Teacher Education
-